

THE INFLUENCE OF STRESS ON THE PERCEPTION OF COMMANDS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Ibroximova Ruhshona Alijon qizi

State University of World Languages Faculty of English Philology (evening
education) Toshkent, Uzbekistan

E-mail: ibrohimovaruhs_hona556@gmail.com

Abstract: This article analyzes the role of stress in the perception of commands in English and Uzbek. The study examines the phonetic, psycholinguistic and pragmatic features of stress revealing similarities and differences between the two languages. Stress and intonation affect the perception of commands, in what cases they are expressed as gentleness or firmness and are also analyzed from the point of view of cultural and linguistic features.

Key words: Stress, intonation, command sentences, phonetics pragmatics, psycholinguistics, English, Uzbek, speech perception.

Introduction: Stress-is strong pronunciation characteristic of distinguishing a syllable or a word using various phonetic means (e.g., the force of exhalation, increasing volume, prolonged pronunciation of the vowel in the syllable, changing pitch. Depending on the object of distinction, two types of stress are recognized: word stress (lexical stress) and phrase stress (logical stress). In Uzbek, stress usually falls on the second syllable: mak-`tab, ki-`tob, va-`tan, ka-pa-`lak, mu-`so-ba-qa.

Word stress

In words with two or more syllables, the syllable pronounced greater intensity is called word stress. Word stress, in turn, is classified into two types depending on which syllable of the word receives stress: fixed stress and free stress.

- Fixed stress: The stress remains on the same syllable regardless of the number of syllable in the word
- Free stress: The stress shift depending on the morphological changes in the word, meaning it moves to the final syllable as the word undergoes affixation. For example, in Uzbek:
 - O'qit -> O'ituv -> O'qituvchi -> O'qituvchilik.

In some cases, word stress plays role in differentiating meaning, such as:

- Olma (verb:” do not take”) vs. Olma (noun:” apple”)

- Osma (verb:” something that is hung”) vs Osma (noun: “medical instrument”).

Phrase stress

Phrase stress highlights an important element within a syntactic structure by distinguishing a key word from the rest of phrase.

Where the phrase stress is placed determines the most important part of the information being conveyed. For example:

- `Olim tomorqada ishladi.
- Olim `tomorqada ishladi.

English has three types of stress (word stress, sentence stress and logical stress).

In English, 85% of words have stress on the first syllable: `garden, `yellow, `trolley-bus.

- Word stress-The emphasis on one of syllable in a word.
- Sentence stress-In a phrase or sentences, certain words are pronounced more strongly than others. These words carry the main meaning and are usually nouns, main verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. Function words such as pronouns, prepositions, articles, modals, conjunctions, and auxiliaries receive less stress.
 - Ann came late
 - She is a `good girl.
- Logical stress-during speech, emphasis on a particular word can attract the listener’s attention or express the speaker’s emotions. This is called logical stress. The stressed word is pronounced with a higher pitch and stronger emphasis. Examples:
 - Where is my pen?
 - It’s `on the table.

Stress and Intonation play a crucial role in speech perception. In command sentences, stress directly affects how the listener interprets the command. The perception of commands in English and Uzbek languages are closely related to the distribution of stress and the intonation system. In English, stress and intonation determine whether a command sound formal or informal. For example: in “Sit down!”, stress on “Sit” makes the command more authoritative. In Uzbek, both stress and grammatical structure influence how a command is perceived:” O’tiring!” sounds more formal, while “o’tir!” can be either friendly or strict.

This article examines the role of stress in the perception of command sentences in English and Uzbek from phonetic, pragmatic and psycholinguistic perspectives.

Research Methods

The study employed the following methods:

1. Comparative analysis-comparing the phonetic and intonational features of command sentences in English and Uzbek.
2. Psycholinguistic experiment-analyzing how listeners perceive commands with different stress patterns.
3. Review of theoretical literature-studying previous linguistic, psycholinguistic, and phonetic research.
4. Experimental phonetics-analyzing the pronunciation and intonational various of commands using acoustic analysis tools.

The Influence of Stress on the Perception of Commands

1. Phonetics and Prosody

The way commands are pronounced and where the stress falls significantly affects their perception.

English:

- Stress usually falls on the main verb or the word carrying the most meaning.
- Rising or falling intonation determines whether a command sounds formal or informal.
- Example:
 1. "Listen carefully!" (Stress on "carefully" emphasizes attentiveness.)
 2. "Sit down!" (Stress on "sit" makes the command firm.)

Uzbek:

- Stress and Intonation may follow a rising or falling pattern.
- The perception of commands is also influenced by verb form and grammatical politeness.
- Example:
 1. "Kel!" (Direct and firm)
 2. "Keling!" (More polite form)

2. Pragmatic and Sociolinguistic Aspects

How a command is perceived depends on its stress and intonation:

Language	Stress and Intonation Features	Perceived Command Type
English	Stress falls on the main verb or key word. Intonation determines strictness or politeness.	Formal / Informal, strict/ polite command.
Uzbek	Stress is typically on the verb or predicting word. Perception depends on politeness markers.	Perceived as either polite or neutral.

Regarding the specific characteristic of stress and its practical classification, scholars, in English, Russian and Uzbek phonetics have conducted a series of theoretical and empirical scientific studies since the 1940s. Various definitions of word stress or accent have been provided by scholars:

According to B. A. Bogoroditski’s definition, stress is characterized by an increase or decrease in energy associated with articulation and sound production.

D. Jones believes that stress is defined by degree of force in producing sound, resulting from the intensity of the stroke. H. Sweet also supports the view that stress is related to the force of the sound being produced.

Theories

Cognitive Load Theory-this theory, developed by John Sweller, suggests that the human brain has limited capacity for processing information. Under stress, cognitive load increases, which reduces the ability to process language. The agglutinative structure of Uzbek (where words are formed by adding suffixes) increases cognitive load, as it requires more cognitive resources to analyze words. In English, however, the syntactic structure is more straightforward, making it relatively easier to understand commands under stress.

Transactional Model of Stress-developed by Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman, this model emphasizes the subjective nature of stress. According to this model, stress is not just about external factors but also about external factors but also about how

individuals perceive and respond to those factors. Speakers of English and Uzbek may react differently to stress due to their cultural and linguistic backgrounds. For instance, Uzbek speakers might rely more on social coping mechanisms, which could influence their perception of commands under stress. “The finding of this study align with Cognitive Load Theory. While the clear syntactic structure of English facilitates command comprehension under stress, the agglutinative nature and prosodic reliance of Uzbek increase cognitive load. Additionally, the Transaction Model of Stress help explain how stress affects command perception differently across cultural and linguistic contexts”.

Conclusion: The perception of commands in English and Uzbek depends on stress and intonation, with each language following its unique prosodic rules. In English, stress and pitch movement define whether a command is polite or strict, while in Uzbek, stress interacts with grammatical politeness makers. Understanding these differences is essential for translation, linguistics, and language learning, marking this topic highly relevant for further research.

References:

1. Wells, J, C. (2006) English Intonation: An introduction.
2. Menn, L. (2017) Psycholinguistics: Introduction and Application.
3. Wardhaugh, R. (2011). An Introduction to Sociolinguistics.
4. Kholmatov, Sh. (2017) Characteristic of Word Stress in English and Uzbek.
5. Saynzarova, M. (2024) The Importance of Stress and Speech Perception in English and Uzbek.
6. Iskandarova, A. & Yusupov, SH, R. (2022) Teaching Exclamatory and Imperative Sentences.
7. Qosimova, D & Qosimov, D. Ingiliz tilini o'rganuvchilar uchun qo'llanma.
8. Xo'jamova, S, G' & Norkulova, R, G'. Ingiliz va O'zbek tillarida so'z urg'usiga berilgan nazariy qarashar.